

Role of the Management in the World Driven by the Industry 4.0

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Abstract

The Artificial Intelligence and connectivity between machines are the essences of the Industry 4.0 revolution. These rapid changes create challenges for the management and are the main reason for the question about its further role. There are differences between natural and artificial intelligence. Although artificial intelligence supports the decision making by a human now in very narrow fields, there are questions related to the replacement of people for example in the oncology hospitals network and change management in the inter-organizational networks. These doubts revolve around decisions making process, Artificial Intelligence development and management itself, therefore this paper present a theoretical discussion and research assumptions about the role of management in the world driven by the Industry 4.0 revolution.

Keywords: Decision-making, Industry 4.0, Inter-organizational Networks

Introduction

Industry 4.0 Revolution (hereinafter IR 4.0 or Industry 4.0) is a concept relating to the use of automation in industries, data processing and data exchange (Niemczyk and Trzaska, 2020). This concept also encompasses Artificial Intelligence (AI) and the digitization of the production process, introducing new technologies. These rapid changes create challenges for the management and are the main reason for the question about its further role. Industry 4.0 is quite well defined idea of the ongoing technological changes in many entities both private and public sector (Michalski et al., 2018; Rosienkiewicz et al., 2018)

Therefore, this paper attempts to explore and synthesize issues related to the creating an inter-organizational networks to achieve growth and development of organisations (Stańczyk-Hugiet et al., 2017). These concerns are based on the making decision process and the role of the management in the world driven by the IR 4.0. The Industry 4.0 is intertwined with the AI and its impact on the management (Lichtarski et al., 2014), what provokes deep philosophical reflection about the technological progress, opportunities and risks related to the technical philosophy (Sulich and Zema, 2017).

In this paper some research assumptions related to the Industry 4.0 concept are presented. These are difference between artificial and natural intelligence, similarity of collective intelligence and inter-organizational network performance. The reason of undertaking such problem is fact, that until now, organizations that have invested in acquiring knowledge or information and human resources have usually been successful in management (Hernes and Nguyen, 2007; Stańczyk-Hugiet et al., 2017). Modern organizations (and their members) operate in the "age of the big data", and overabundance of information, therefore, to be successful they need to perform better decision taking using IR 4.0 solutions (Lu, 2017). Currently, however, organizations that still invest in their assets and employees, these organization still are not successful and they have to compete with artificial intelligence (Hernes and Nguyen, 2007; Kuik et al., 2019; Lichtarski et al., 2014). The other companies try to gain advantage

creating an inter-organizational networks (Lichtarski et al., 2014) and use the synergy effect or to use a collective intelligence (Krupski et al., 2017) collective learning or knowledge management (Vaidya et al., 2018).

The presented in this paper research assumptions and definitions are related to the ongoing research which is dedicated to the relationships in the inter-organizational network (Zema and Sulich, 2019) created by the entities of Environmental Goods and Services Sector (EGSS) (Zema and Sulich, 2019). The connection to the Industry 4.0 in such specific sector is more expected than in others because of lower attractiveness of jobs dedicated to waste treatment and recycling. Also in this article the other examples of the researches on the inter-organizational networks are presented to draw our own study dedicated to the oncological hospitals inter-organizational network in Poland (Sus et al., 2019; Sus and Organa, 2020), which is the second research project that will benefit from the results of this article. Presented networks are related to the our research project, due to limited awareness among businesses regarding their specificity, prevalence and consequences of adopting IR 4.0 (Rüssmann et al., 2015). The adopted method used in this article was the literature review. The main finding of this study is that in the inter-organizational networks are one of the opportunities coming from the IR 4.0 positive impact. The IR 4.0 is a stimulus for both cooperation and organizational innovation and the development of inter-organizational networks. In future research the IR 4.0 will be analysed in terms of its impact on present-day organizations and the changes that occur in cooperation between companies in inter-organizational networks.

Impact of Industry 4.0 on the Management Sciences

Industry 4.0 Revolution generate significant issues to still large group of organisations and often create challenges and opportunities related to the processes of their further growth (quantitative changes) or improvements and development (qualitative changes) (Michalski et al., 2018; Stańczyk-Hugiet et al., 2019; Sung, 2018). Therefore IR 4.0 has an influence on organisation's management and the cooperation between them. This revolution changes everything in business and classic passive matching strategies will be ineffective (Niemczyk et al., 2018; Niemczyk and Trzaska, 2020; Schlingensiepen et al., 2016; Stańczyk-Hugiet et al., 2011). Strategic management process is striving to achieve the organization's objectives (Sus and Organa, 2020), and is based on the relevance of factors coming from the business environment (Chlebus et al., 2019; Michalski et al., 2018).

The professional literature of the subject (Gwóźdź and Parkitna, 2015; Niemczyk et al., 2012; Stańczyk-Hugiet et al., 2019) attempts to give inter-organizational networks a diverse theoretical framework with a wide spectrum from sociology, computer science through economics to management (Zema and Sulich, 2019). The interdisciplinary nature of considerations and research in the field of inter-organizational networks allows for a better recognition of their nature, functioning principles and significance for the functioning of the economy (Lichtarski, 2017; Zhong et al., 2017). The most-exposed reference theories in social sciences are transaction cost theory (economics), social network theory (sociology), and resource theory (strategic management) (Krupski et al., 2017). According to resource theory (resource-based view), competitive advantage depends on having or access to the appropriate resources (Sus et al., 2019). The resources giving a competitive advantage should therefore be valuable but scarce (rare) (Stańczyk-Hugiet et al., 2017). Resource based view assumes that there is no enterprise that has all the resources it needs (Niemczyk et al., 2012). Resources scarcity results in paying attention to the association of the organization with the business environment being the source of resources that the organization is not able to independently produce (Lichtarski and Niemczyk, 2015; Niemczyk and Trzaska, 2020). The desire to fill the resource gap pushes organizations seeking to maintain or gain a competitive advantage to establish inter-organizational ties and enter a network of collaboration (inter-organizational network) (Niemczyk et al., 2012). The networks are made up of at least two autonomous organizations that are becoming more similar to each other with time and the growing use of information technology (Kolberg and Zühlke, 2015; Lu, 2017). The necessity of cooperation with many stakeholders and business partners can bring surprises, discouragement and resistance in relation to the changes required in modern organisations which implement IR 4.0 infrastructure (Barreto et al., 2017; Hernes, 2019). This infrastructure is crucial not only for the management and information change, but also create a similarity between autonomous organizations

in the network. There are sectors in which not networked activities are impossible. However, the cooperation between organizations in the network brings more positive than negative effects (Gąbka et al., 2016; Niemczyk et al., 2012). Implementation of the IR 4.0 in the organizations allow them to form a network and to gain some organisational proximity (Lichtarski, 2017). Organizational proximity is a key property of cooperating organizations. Additionally the Artificial Intelligence can influence: explaining sources of competitiveness and efficiency as well as stages and conditions for development; identification of basic features and characteristics of nodes - transfer of research attention from ties to network nodes, identification and characteristics of relationships on the line of cooperation in networks and types of innovation (Chlebus and Rosienkiewicz, 2011; Michalski et al., 2018; Piórkowska and Lichtarski, 2016; Sung, 2018). Industry 4.0 in organization management favours: sharing information, knowledge and technology, thereby accelerating the implementation of innovation; intensifying development thanks to the effective benefits of cooperation; building inter-organizational trust reducing the level of business uncertainty.

Artificial and Natural Intelligence

The AI is often demonstrated in the contrast to the natural intelligence (Hernes and Nguyen, 2007; Rosienkiewicz, 2013) possessed by any of natural object, especially by the humans or animals (Sung, 2018). Human intelligence is based on the multiple cognitive abilities to learn, form concepts, understand, apply logic, and reason, including the capacities to recognize patterns, comprehend ideas, plan, solve problems, make decisions, retain information, and use language to communicate (Reinhard et al., 2016). Natural intelligence is measurable by different tests. Additionally according to the multiple intelligence theory there is no single human intelligence, but variety of them used in different context or situation interchangeably (Rojko, 2017). Multiple intelligence theory assumes that there are types of intelligence such as (Hernes, 2019): logical-mathematical, spatial, linguistic, musical, social (interpersonal), bodily-kinesthetic etc., used by human with elasticity in action, although one of this type can be leading one. Although we can observe the results of the intelligence, it is very hard to understand what it is. There are of course different tests measuring the intelligence, but they are also criticised because some of the require some knowledge and they can be not applicable in different cultures or even languages (Xu et al., 2018). Brain therefore can be understood as a biological infrastructure for the mind functions (natural algorithm) which combined effects creates intelligence phenomenon (Fig.1).

Fig. 1: Brain is an infrastructure for the mind functions used in natural intelligence phenomena. Authors' own elaboration.

Measurement of the intelligence among people or their individual achievement observation allow to distinguish group of genius. However, science recognised multiple examples of individuals, called savants, who possessed extraordinary narrow type of intelligence with dysfunction of other intelligence types. Savant syndrome is a condition in which someone with significant mental disabilities demonstrates certain abilities far in excess of average. There is also natural intelligence observed among animals. Intelligent creatures in a natural environment evolved and through the biological evolution (Vaidya et al., 2018) gained the biological infrastructure and capabilities to develop their intelligence. The bigger animals (vertebrates especially) has individual intelligence, although smaller (invertebrates) are sometimes characterised by the collective intelligence to achieve cognition, cooperation and coordination. The goal of collective intelligence is mutual recognition and enrichment of individuals. The collective intelligence phenomenon in the inter-organizational network is going to be discussed in the next sub-chapter. What is important collective intelligence group intelligence that emerges from the collaboration, collective efforts, and competition of many individuals and appears in consensus decision making.

The one of the proposed definition of AI is a this, which assume that it is "the ability of the system to adapt its operation in order to achieve the assumed goal in the environment in which it is located" (Zhong et al., 2017).

Artificial intelligence (AI) is a type of intelligence performed by any human-made machine equipped by the program or algorithm. Therefore, artificial intelligence aims to mimic human cognitive functions related to the problem solving and learning (Niemczyk and Trzaska, 2020; Stańczyk-Hugiet et al., 2011; Sus and Organa, 2020). Artificiality of this intelligence is caused by algorithm-based intelligence functions demonstrated by the computer program. It is often stated that algorithm is not elastic, but highly specialized and therefore its performance is higher than average human. This disproportion of effectiveness of undertaken action such decision making is visible especially in: decoding or

deciphering information, taking decision in business, market games, games and sport or searching for the unknown objects on the photos taken by telescope.

There are experiments which examine intelligence both natural and artificial. The most interesting is the Turing's test which is used to determine whether or not a computer is capable of thinking like a human being. On the one hand, generally humans are less effective when complicated mathematical patterns have to be used. On the other hand, it is very difficult to create an algorithm which can successfully recognize different human faces and the emotions of observed people, combined with situations. There are also works to help people with the security protection for example to prevent terrorist attacks. The AI can support human intelligence and inventiveness in areas which demand action and such is environment protection.

Chess Algorithms and Computers with Artificial Intelligence

The researches based on the automation of human calculations by mathematical algorithms began many years before modern microchip computers. The idea of computer invention was simple to help scientists perform fast calculations with great numbers related to the rocket industry. Some of scientist concerned an idea of artificial intelligence, which would mimic the human intelligence not in proteins but in silica. Their goal was to communicate with a computer and ask questions, to obtain best answers. The real revolution in Artificial intelligence began in 1950, when article titled "Programming a computer for playing chess" by Claude E. Shannon was published (Shannon, 1950). In his paper Shannon concerned with the problem of the constructing a computer routine or program for a modern general-purpose computer which will be enable it to play chess. Shannon predicted that this simple theoretical deliberation can bring a satisfactory solution for problems of a greater significance (Shannon, 1950). Proposed algorithm was simple, based on the computer which consider using the algorithm the current configuration of chess pieces. The computer considers using the algorithm the current configuration of all chess pieces and all their moves. The algorithm assigns a numerical value (evaluation function) to each move, which assesses how good the move is (Shannon, 1950). Subsequent moves made with chess pieces are evaluated and further moves with the highest value of the evaluation function are anticipated. The algorithm logic has been developed so much that in 1997 computer "Deep Blue" won chess match with world chess champion Garry Kasparov. Algorithm was improved by programmers and best chess players, and its latest form is called Stockfish chess engine. The algorithm was based on human experience, and it was supervised learning.

Completely other approach was to train algorithm in neuron network, which is unsupervised learning. There are no predefined assumptions (except basic game rules) in neural network learning, such as best moves. The algorithm must somehow come up with the best moves itself, it starts with the random structure of the algorithm steps, whose steps are strengthened if they lead to the expected result. Other alternative algorithm steps are not considered over time.

Management and Decision Taking

In recent years extended discussion concerning new trends in modern management and the challenges facing managers of contemporary organizations have been triggered repeatedly (Michalski et al., 2018). What is explored in this debate are the new demands related to dynamic, unpredictable and disruptive technological changes (Kolberg and Zühlke, 2015; Xu et al., 2018), and new expectations and requirements towards employees. Management is the most human action, making a decision is based on many factors, which computers can compute faster. Although their performance is higher than human (in this sense that any decision made by computer is far better, made faster, efficient than taken by human (Rüssmann et al., 2015; Stock and Seliger, 2016), it has to be said that machines will never become a human, and human never is going to become the machine. The decision process in the case of man consists of two thought processes: inventive and decision-making (Figure 2).

Human decision making is different from algorithms and machine learning methods described. The simplest form of making decisions consists of three phases: determining the set of action variants,

assessing them, and choosing the option considered the most advantageous (Bogdan et al., 1981; Nosal, 2001). Human thinking is sequential, so the algorithms reflect the stages of human thinking. The main reason for such organization of the decision-making process is the complexity of the situation and cognitive limitations experienced by members of the organization. People making key decisions in organizations naturally strive to expand the sequence of decision-making steps, but on the other hand it extends the time needed. The limited resources, the growing number of options for action, contradictory assessments and the lack of clear decisions lead to the search for an organization with which relationships can be established and cooperation to solve a problem or make a decision (Klimas, 2015).

In figure 2 presented the decision-making phases in two reference systems. The first of these covers the basic sequence of phases of related results and control questions. The second form of presentation captures decision thinking as a process involving "deviations" caused by various psychological factors. Convergence in the decision-making process means that this variant of decision thinking means that this variant of action, which will become a decision, did not appear by accident (Nosal, 2001). Moreover, the sequence of decision making phases gradually leads to a narrowing of results, enabling final settlement (Nosal, 2001).

Fig. 2: Convergence of the decision-making process. Authors' own elaboration based on (Nosal, 2001).

Naming a computer code an Artificial Intelligence, which means that it can mimic functionality of brain, to some of people is somehow offensive. This term has been invented to rise this type of feelings. Some people, when they hear it automatically get triggered and contrary to that, there are people who see AI as promise of better future. Either way, everyone will admit that this mixed usage of biological and IT terms rises a discussion at many levels. At the most recent, looking at the peoples' attitude to AI it seems like majority of humanity decided, that if they cannot stop it, they may also enjoy the ride and get accustomed to self-driving vehicles, custom phone applications, but also chat bots and surveillance of public activities.

Network Organization

The inter-organizational network is a system of at least two independent and independent organizations (diad), connected with each other by a set of bonds for cooperation (Klimas, 2014). The inter-organizational network is a system composed of long-term, non-incident connections of entities oriented on the relation of convergent goals (Ćwik et al., 2017; Klimas, 2012). In the description of the inter-organizational network based on graph theory, the organizations forming the network are called network nodes or vertices, while long-term relationships (inter-organizational ties, connections) oriented towards achieving common goals are called edges (Sulich et al., 2019). The application of graph theory allows to trace the processes occurring in the network, including determining the direction of interactions. The process that can reveal the existence and elements of an inter-organizational network is the product life cycle management (Sus and Organa, 2020). However, in the case of an inter-organizational network within the sector of environmental goods and services this process can be a waste recycling, e.g. waste tyres. This sector provides a wide spectrum for the usage of the robots and AI combined with the image recognition.

The adopted in this paper definition of the network organisation recognise it as a set of entities and relatively lasting ties between them. The main element defining the network are cooperative ties. The strength of the bond is based on trust and long-term contracts (Sulich et al., 2019).

Relationships in the Network Organisation

The natural intelligence is performed also by a group of animals. For example, ants exhibit some form of natural intelligence as a colony or in a swarm of bees. The similar natural collective intelligence can be observed among birds and fishes (the different species of fish) when they form a shoal. There is a similarity between biological forms of cooperation and these observed in the business environment.

Among the factors conducive to generating market advantage in management sciences are long-term inter-organizational interactions, participation in inter-organizational networks and availability of network resources (Klimas, 2015; Stańczyk-Hugiet et al., 2019). Inter-organizational relations on the market may take the form of coexistence, cooperation, competition and cooptation (Czakon, 2007; Czetwertyński, 2016; Kabarowski et al., 2006). These four relationship forms exist in parallel, but not proportionally in the space of economic practice (Klimas, 2014).

On the basis of strategic management, cooperation is seen as:

- a multi-entity activity aiming at achieving mutually consistent goals (Klimas, 2012),
- a dynamic and separate competences of the organization strengthening competitiveness (Klimas, 2014) and contributing to the increase of competitive advantage (Klimas, 2015);
- a type of knowledge management strategy (Dudek-Godeau et al., 2016; Sulich, 2018) in organizations used to create new, non-existent knowledge (Lichtarski, 2013).

The purpose of creating relationships in the network organization is to increase management competence and increase the flow of information between entities to improve their cooperation.

Cooperation is crucial for creating a network consist of independent organisations (Sulich et al., 2019). Moreover, the network organization gains an advantage over the other networks in the environment, due to the synergy effects. Humans and AI already collaborate: AI know best way in the traffic, drive autonomously or is able to find more efficient ways in the processes. In those examples human acknowledges, the results that AI delivers, because it improves the outcome. In the future AI itself might find best organisations to cooperate with. In industry 4.0 the machines can interact with each other and creating a similar network. Nevertheless, to reach such AI communication, the organizations cannot encapsulate their data to potential competitor (Stańczyk-Hugiet et al., 2019).

Conclusions

The modern economy based on knowledge and intelligence is characterized by networking (creation of inter-organizational networks). Organizations operate in a network economy supported by infrastructure solutions (development of information technologies and artificial intelligence) and cooperation relationships. The network economy is characterized by above-average dynamics, process orientation, chaos, lack of boundaries, unpredictability and promotion of intangible resources and cooperation processes between organizations (Klimas, 2014). Therefore, organizational efficiency and market advantage are generated due to network membership. The exchange of tangible and intangible resources, reciprocity and commitment are essential for the development of the network (Sus et al., 2019).

The artificial intelligence, which arose in the 20th century, transforms our reality and future. IR 4.0 organizes our reality and influences decision making (Niemczyk et al., 2012). The digitization is advancing in all areas of life from public administration, education, production and hobby implementation. In the literature, definitions of artificial intelligence boil down to determining that it is an attempt to model aspects of human reasoning using computers, or an attempt to solve using computers such problems that are usually solved by a human.

The conditions of the modern economy are privileged by innovative organizations, using the latest technologies, which fall under IR 4.0. This is because pioneering and innovation are one of the cornerstones of the competitive advantage sought by organizations. They subordinate their activities to the requirements of the market game, putting emphasis in their strategies, processes and activities on increasing the level of innovation. IR 4.0 IR 4.0 decides about inter-organizational cooperation, improves learning, creation, absorption and commercialization of knowledge.

The implementation of the Industry 4.0 concept necessitates involvement from top management promoting comprehensive change management activities and processes for arranging organizational and production structures according to the needs of the connected value creation. A collaborative, explorative, and entrepreneurial mind-set is a success factor that is necessary to establish among a company's most important resource: the employees.

Managers should have willingness to convince employees of the beneficial nature of Industry 4.0 and to address their concerns actively. By analysing the Industry 4.0 studies published so far, it has been discovered that they mostly discuss the technical aspects but do not pay attention to managerial approaches and organisational culture that are a significant factor influencing the success of the implementation of this concept. Implementing the Industry 4.0 concept requires continuous innovation and education that not only depend on people's abilities but also on organisational culture. Research has shown that successful organisations will be those that disperse decision making processes related to the leadership and managerial responsibilities throughout a network in the organisation.

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